

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1342709>

ISSN 2225-6717

Volume 43

2018

The Papers of Independent Authors

**Aviation and Cosmonautics
Chemistry and Physics
Physics and Astronomy**

Solomon I. Khmelnik

New solution of Maxwell's equations for spherical wave

Contents

1. Introduction
 2. Solution of the Maxwell's equations
 3. Energy Flows
 4. Conclusion
- Appendix 1
References
Tables

Annotation

It is noted that the known solution for a spherical electromagnetic wave does not satisfy the law of conservation of energy (it is retained only on the average), the electric and magnetic intensities of the same name (by coordinates) are in phase, only one from system of Maxwell's equations is satisfied, the solution is not wave solution, there is no flow of energy with real value. A solution is offered that is free from these shortcomings.

1. Introduction

In [1] a solution of the Maxwell equations for a spherical wave in the far field was proposed. Next, we consider the solution of Maxwell's equations for a spherical wave in the entire region of existence of a wave (without splitting into bands). Such a problem arises in the solution of the equations of electrodynamics for an elementary electric dipole-vibrator. The solution of this problem is known and it is on the basis of this solution that the antennas are constructed. However, this solution has a number of shortcomings, in particular [2],

1. The energy conservation law is satisfied only on the average,
2. The solution is inhomogeneous and it is practically necessary to divide it into separate zones (as a rule, near, middle and far), in which the solutions turn out to be completely different,
3. In the near zone there is no flow of energy with the real value

4. The magnetic and electrical components are in phase,
5. In the near zone, the solution is not wave (i.s. the distance is not an argument of the trigonometric function),
6. The known solution does not satisfy Maxwell's system of equations (a solution that satisfies a single equation of the system can not be considered a solution of the system of equations).

In Fig. 1 [8] shows the picture of the lines of force of the electric field, constructed on the basis of the known solution. Obviously, such a picture can not exist in a spherical wave.

In practice, specified drawbacks of the known solution mean that they (mathematical solutions) do not strictly describe the real characteristics of technical devices. A more rigorous solution, when applied in the design systems of such devices, must certainly improve their quality.

Fig. 1.

2. Solution of the Maxwell's equations

So, we will use spherical coordinates. Fig. 1 shows the spherical coordinate system (ρ, θ, φ) . Next, we will place the formulas in tables and use the following notation:

T (table_number) - (column_number) - (line_number)

Table T1-3 lists the expressions for the rotor and the divergence of the vector E in these coordinates [3]. Here and below

- E is electrical intensities,
- H is magnetic intensities,
- J is the density of the electric displacement current,
- M is the density of the magnetic displacement current,
- μ is absolute magnetic permeability,
- ε is absolute dielectric constant.

Fig. 1.

We establish the following notation:

$$\Psi(E_\rho) = \frac{E_\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial E_\rho}{\partial \rho} \tag{1}$$

$$T(E_\varphi) = \left(\frac{E_\varphi}{\text{tg}(\theta)} + \frac{\partial(E_\varphi)}{\partial(\theta)} \right) \tag{2}$$

With these designations taken into account, the formulas in Table **T1-3** take the form given in Table **T1-4**. In the table **T1A-2** we write the Maxwell equations.

Thus, there are eight Maxwell equations with six unknowns. This system is overdetermined. It is generally accepted that there are no radial tensions in the spherical wave (although this has not been proved). In this case, a system of eight Maxwell equations with four unknowns appears. A solution of this problem was found in [1]. In essence, there is a solution of 4 equations (see **T1A-2.2, 3, 6, 7**). In this solution, the intensities functions have the same factor for all functions - the function $g(\theta)$ of the argument θ . The remaining 4 equations are satisfied for a certain choice of this function. This solution turns out to be such that it

We have to admit that in a spherical wave there are radial intensities. However, even so, the system of Maxwell's equations remains redefined. Let us also assume that there are radial electric currents of displacement. This assumption does not remove the problem of

overdetermination, but adds one more problem. The point is that the sphere has an ideal symmetry and the solution must obviously be symmetrical.

It is suggested that there are also radial **magnetic displacement currents**. Such an assumption does not require the existence of magnetic monopoles as well, the existence of electric displacement currents does not follow from the existence of electric charges.

Next, we will look for the solution in the form of the functions E, H, J, M, presented in **Table T2-2**, where the actual functions of the form $g(\theta)$ and $e(\rho)$, $h(\rho)$, $j(\rho)$, $m(\rho)$ are to be calculated, and the coefficients χ , α , ω are known.

Under these conditions, we transform the formulas **T1-3** into **T1-4**, where the following notations are adopted:

$$\boxed{e_\varphi} = \frac{\partial(e_\varphi(\rho))}{\partial(\rho)}, \tag{3}$$

$$q = \kappa\rho + \omega t \tag{4}$$

From (2, 4) we find:

$$T(E_\varphi) = \left(\frac{\sin(\theta)}{\text{tg}(\theta)} + \cos(\theta) \right) e_\varphi \cos(q) = 2e_\varphi \cos(\theta) \cos(q) \tag{5}$$

Similarly,

$$T(E_\theta) = 2e_\theta \cos(\theta) \sin(q) \tag{6}$$

$$T(H_\varphi) = 2h_\varphi \cos(\theta) \sin(q) \tag{7}$$

$$T(H_\theta) = 2h_\theta \cos(\theta) \cos(q) \tag{8}$$

With these designations taken into account, the formulas in **Table T1-3** take the form given in **Table T1-4**.

Further, using the above formulas and using the formulas from **Table T2**, we construct the tables **T2i**, **T2ρ**, **T2Ψ**.

In **Table T3-2** we write the Maxwell equations. Further, we take condition

$$\alpha = 0 \tag{9}$$

We substitute the rotors and divergences from **Table T1-4** into **T1A-2** equations, take into account condition (9), shorten the obtained expressions on the functions of argument θ and write the result in **Table T1A-3**. Then substitute the functions from the tables **T2i**, **T2ρ**, **T2Ψ** in the function **T1A-3** and write the result in **Table T4-2**. In this table, we use the notation of the form

$$\text{si} = \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t), \tag{10}$$

$$\text{co} = \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t). \quad (11)$$

Further, each equation in Table **T4-2** is replaced by two equations, one of which contains terms with a factor **si** and the other with a factor **co**. The result will be written in Table **T5-2**.

Equations **T5-2-2, 6, 3, 7** have a solution, found in [1] and having the following form (which can be verified by direct substitution):

$$\chi = \frac{\omega}{c} \sqrt{\varepsilon\mu} \quad (12)$$

$$e_\varphi = A/\rho, e_\theta = A/\rho, \quad (13)$$

$$h_\varphi = -B/\rho, h_\theta = B/\rho, \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{B}{A} = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \quad (15)$$

Consider the equations **T5-2.4, T5-2.8**. Their solution is considered in Appendix 1, where functions $e_\rho(\rho)$, $\bar{e}_\rho(\rho)$, $h_\rho(\rho)$, $\bar{h}_\rho(\rho)$ are found. After this, the functions $j_\rho(\rho)$, $\bar{j}_\rho(\rho)$, $m_\rho(\rho)$, $\bar{m}_\rho(\rho)$ can be found using the equations **T5-2.1, T5-2.5**.

This completes the task.

In particular, for $A=B$ and a small value of χ , these functions take the following form:

$$h_\rho = e_\rho - \frac{1}{\rho}(G + 2A \cdot \ln(\rho)), \quad (16)$$

$$\bar{h}_\rho = \bar{e}_\rho = \frac{D}{\rho}, \quad (17)$$

$$j_\rho = \frac{2A}{\rho^2} - \frac{\mu\omega}{c} \cdot \frac{D}{\rho}, \quad (18)$$

$$\bar{j}_\rho = -\frac{\mu\omega}{c} \cdot \frac{1}{\rho}(G + 2A \cdot \ln(\rho)), \quad (19)$$

$$m_\rho = -\frac{2B}{\rho^2} + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} \cdot \frac{D}{\rho}, \quad (20)$$

$$\bar{m}_\rho = -\frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} \cdot \frac{1}{\rho}(G + 2A \cdot \ln(\rho)). \quad (21)$$

Here

G is a constant that can take different values for the functions e_ρ and h_ρ ,

D is a constant that can take different values for the functions \bar{e}_ρ and \bar{h}_ρ .

3. Energy Flows

Density of electromagnetic energy flow - Poynting vector

$$S = \eta E \times H, \quad (1)$$

where

$$\eta = c/4\pi. \quad (2)$$

In the SI system formula (1) takes the form:

$$S = E \times H. \quad (3)$$

In spherical coordinates φ , θ , ρ the flux density of electromagnetic energy has three components S_φ , S_θ , S_ρ , directed along the radius, along the circumference, along the axis, respectively. It was shown in [4] that they are determined by the formula

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S_\varphi \\ S_\theta \\ S_\rho \end{bmatrix} = \eta(E \times H) = \eta \begin{bmatrix} E_\theta H_\rho - E_\rho H_\theta \\ E_\rho H_\varphi - E_\varphi H_\rho \\ E_\varphi H_\theta - E_\theta H_\varphi \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

We first find a radial flux of energy. Substituting in here the formulas from Table **T2** and (1.4, 2.13, 2.14), we find:

$$\begin{aligned} S_\rho &= \frac{A}{\rho} \sin(\theta) \sin(q) \frac{B}{\rho} \sin(\theta) \sin(q) - \frac{A}{\rho} \sin(\theta) \cos(q) \frac{-B}{\rho} \sin(\theta) \cos(q) \\ &= \frac{AB}{\rho^2} \sin^2(\theta) (\sin^2(q) + \cos^2(q)) \end{aligned}$$

or, taking into account (2.15),

$$S_\rho = \frac{A^2}{\rho^2} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \sin^2(\theta) \quad (5)$$

Note that the surface area of a sphere with a radius ρ is $4\pi\rho^2$. Then the flow of energy passing through a sphere with a radius ρ is

$$\overline{S}_\rho = \int_\theta 4\pi \rho^2 S_\rho d\theta = -4\pi\rho^2 \eta \frac{A^2}{\rho^2} \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \int_\theta \sin^2(\theta) d\theta$$

or

$$\overline{S}_\rho = -4\pi\eta A^2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \int_0^{2\pi} \sin^2(\theta) d\theta$$

or

$$\overline{S}_\rho = -4\pi^2 \eta A^2 \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \quad (6)$$

Thus, the energy flux density passing through the sphere does not depend on the radius and does not depend on time, i.e. this flux has the same value on a spherical surface of any radius at any instant of time. In other words, the energy flux directed along the radius retains its value with increasing radius and does not depend on time, which corresponds to the law of conservation of energy.

4. Conclusion

1. A solution of Maxwell's equations, free from the above disadvantages, is presented in Table T2.

2. The solution is monochromatic.

3. The amplitudes of the transverse wave intensities are proportional to ρ^{-1} .

4. The electric and magnetic intensities of the same name (according to coordinates ρ , φ , θ) are phase shifted by a quarter of a period.

5. The energy flux directed along the radius retains its value with increasing radius and does not depend on time, which corresponds to the law of conservation of energy.

6. There are radial electric and magnetic intensities.

7. There are radial electric and magnetic displacement currents.

Fig. 3.

Appendix 1.

From T5-4.1 and (2.13) we:

$$\bar{\bar{e}}_\rho = -\frac{1}{\chi} \boxed{e_\rho} - \frac{1}{\chi\rho} e_\rho - \frac{2A}{\chi\rho^2}. \quad (1)$$

Differentiating (1), we obtain:

$$\boxed{\bar{\bar{e}}_\rho} = -\frac{1}{\chi} \boxed{\boxed{e_\rho}} - \frac{1}{\chi\rho} \boxed{e_\rho} + \frac{1}{\chi\rho^2} e_\rho + \frac{4A}{\chi\rho^3}. \quad (2)$$

We substitute (2) in T5-4.2 and find:

$$\left(-\frac{1}{\chi\rho} \boxed{e_\rho} - \frac{1}{\chi\rho^2} e_\rho - \frac{2A}{\chi\rho^3} - \chi e_\rho - \frac{1}{\chi} \boxed{\boxed{e_\rho}} - \frac{1}{\chi\rho} \boxed{e_\rho} + \frac{1}{\chi\rho^2} e_\rho + \frac{4A}{\chi\rho^3} \right) = 0$$

or

$$\boxed{e_\rho} + \frac{2}{\rho} \boxed{e_\rho} + \chi^2 e_\rho - \frac{2A}{\rho^3} = 0. \tag{3}$$

From this differential equation one can find the function $e_\rho(\rho)$, and from this known function and the differential equation **T5-4.2**, find the function $\bar{e}_\rho(\rho)$.

From **T5-8.1** and (2.14) we:

$$\bar{h}_\rho = \frac{1}{\chi} \boxed{h_\rho} + \frac{1}{\chi\rho} h_\rho + \frac{2B}{\chi\rho^2}. \tag{4}$$

Differentiating (4), we obtain:

$$\boxed{\bar{h}_\rho} = \frac{1}{\chi} \boxed{\bar{h}_\rho} + \frac{1}{\chi\rho} \boxed{h_\rho} - \frac{1}{\chi\rho^2} h_\rho - \frac{4B}{\chi\rho^3}. \tag{5}$$

We substitute (5) in **T5-8.2** and find:

$$\left(\frac{1}{\chi\rho} \boxed{h_\rho} + \frac{1}{\chi\rho^2} h_\rho + \frac{2B}{\chi\rho^3} + \chi h_\rho + \frac{1}{\chi} \boxed{\bar{h}_\rho} + \frac{1}{\chi\rho} \boxed{h_\rho} - \frac{1}{\chi\rho^2} h_\rho - \frac{4B}{\chi\rho^3} \right) = 0$$

or

$$\boxed{h_\rho} + \frac{2}{\rho} \boxed{h_\rho} + \chi^2 h_\rho - \frac{2B}{\rho^3} = 0 \tag{6}$$

From this differential equation one can find the function $h_\rho(\rho)$, and from this known function and the differential equation **T5-8.2**, find the function $\bar{h}_\rho(\rho)$.

In particular, for $\varepsilon = \mu$, for example, for a vacuum, we find from (2.15) that $A=B$ and, comparing (3) and (6), we find that

$$h_\rho = e_\rho. \tag{7}$$

If $A=B$ and the value of χ is small, the equations **T5-4.1** and **T5-8.1** coincide and take the form

$$\dot{y} + \frac{2}{\rho} y - \frac{2A}{\rho^3} = 0, \tag{8}$$

where

$$y = \boxed{h_\rho} = \boxed{e_\rho}. \tag{9}$$

The method for solving such an equation is given in [9, p. 50]. Following this method, we find

$$y = \frac{C+2A\ln(\rho)}{\rho^2} \tag{10}$$

where C is a constant that can take different values for the functions $\boxed{e_\rho}$ and $\boxed{h_\rho}$. From (9, 10) we find:

$$h_\rho = e_\rho = -\frac{C}{\rho} - 2A \left(\frac{1+\ln(\rho)}{\rho} \right) = -\frac{1}{\rho} (G + 2A \cdot \ln(\rho)) \tag{11}$$

where G is a constant that can take different values for the functions e_ρ and h_ρ .

For a small value of χ , the equations **T5-4.1** and **T5-8.1** coincide and take the form

$$\dot{z} + \frac{1}{\rho}z = 0, \quad (12)$$

where

$$z = \bar{h}_\rho = \bar{e}_\rho. \quad (13)$$

The solution of this equation has the form:

$$\bar{h}_\rho = \bar{e}_\rho = \frac{D}{\rho}, \quad (14)$$

where D is a constant that can take different values for the functions \bar{e}_ρ and \bar{h}_ρ .

From **T5-2.1** and (2.13, 14, 11) we:

$$j_\rho = \frac{2}{\rho}e_\varphi - \frac{\mu}{c}\omega\bar{h}_\rho = \frac{2A}{\rho^2} - \frac{\mu\omega}{c} \cdot \frac{D}{\rho}, \quad (15)$$

$$\bar{j}_\rho = \frac{\mu}{c}\omega h_\rho = -\frac{\mu\omega}{c} \cdot \frac{1}{\rho}(G + 2A \cdot \ln(\rho)). \quad (16)$$

From **T5-2.2** and (2.14, 14, 11) we:

$$m_\rho = \frac{2}{\rho}h_\varphi + \frac{\varepsilon}{c}\omega\bar{e}_\rho = -\frac{2B}{\rho^2} + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} \cdot \frac{D}{\rho}, \quad (17)$$

$$\bar{m}_\rho = \frac{\varepsilon}{c}\omega e_\rho = -\frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} \cdot \frac{1}{\rho}(G + 2A \cdot \ln(\rho)). \quad (18)$$

References

1. S.I. Khmelnik New solution of Maxwell's equations for spherical wave in the far zone, in this volume and <http://vixra.org/abs/1711.0243>, 2017-11-13.
2. Yu.V. Pimenov, V.I. Volman, A.D. Muravtsov. Technical electrodynamics. Edited by Yu.V. Pimenov, Moscow, 2002 r., 536 p. (in Russian).
3. Andre Anjo. Mathematics for Electrical and Radio Engineers, publ. "Nauka", Moscow, 1964, 772 p. (in Russian).
4. S.I. Khmelnik. Inconsistency Solution of Maxwell's Equations, publ. "MiC", Israel, Printed in USA, Lulu Inc., ID 19043222, ISBN 978-1-365-23941-0, sixth edition, 2017, 190 p., <http://vixra.org/abs/1607.0423>, 27.07.2017.
5. S.I. Khmelnik. Variational Principle of Extremum in Electromechanical and Electrodynamical Systems, Publisher by "MiC", printed in USA, Lulu Inc., ID 1142842, ISBN 978-0-557-08231-5, Fourth Edition, 2014, 347 c. <http://vixra.org/abs/1402.0026>, 2014-11-10.
6. Near and far zones of the electromagnetic field, <http://lib.izdatelstwo.com/Papers2/BIZ.pdf> (in Russian).

7. V.A. Neganov, D.P. Tabakov, D.P. Yarovoi. Modern theory and practical applications of antennas. Editor Neganov V.A. Publ. «Radio engineering», Moscow, 2009, 720 pages (in Russian).
8. Antennas: Theory and Practice», Sergei A. Schelkunoff and Harald T. Friis, Bell Telephone Laboratories, New York: John Wiley & Sons, 1952.
9. V.F. Zaitsev, A.D. Polyanin. Handbook of ordinary differential equations. Moscow, FIZMATLIT, 2001, 576 p. (in Russian).
10. S.I. Khmel'nik. New solution of Maxwell's equations for spherical wave. The Papers of independent Authors, ISSN 2225-6717, 2018, volume 41, <http://dna.izdatelstwo.com/> (in Russian).

Tables

Table 1.

1	2	3	4
1	$\text{rot}_\rho(E)$	$\frac{E_\varphi}{\rho g(\theta)} + \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\rho \partial \theta} - \frac{\partial E_\theta}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi}$	$\frac{T(E_\varphi)}{\rho} - \frac{i\alpha E_\theta}{\rho \sin(\theta)}$
5	$\text{rot}_\rho(H)$	$\frac{H_\varphi}{\rho g(\theta)} + \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\rho \partial \theta} - \frac{\partial H_\theta}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi}$	$\frac{T(H_\varphi)}{\rho} - \frac{i\alpha H_\theta}{\rho \sin(\theta)}$
2	$\text{rot}_\theta(E)$	$\frac{\partial E_\rho}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi} - \frac{E_\varphi}{\rho} - \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\partial \rho}$	$\frac{i\alpha E_\rho}{\rho \sin(\theta)} - \psi(E_\varphi)$
3	$\text{rot}_\varphi(E)$	$\frac{E_\theta}{\rho} + \frac{\partial E_\theta}{\partial \rho} - \frac{\partial E_\rho}{\rho \partial \varphi}$	$\psi(E_\theta) - \frac{i\alpha E_\rho}{\rho}$
6	$\text{rot}_\theta(H)$	$\frac{\partial H_\rho}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi} - \frac{H_\varphi}{\rho} - \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\partial \rho}$	$\frac{i\alpha H_\rho}{\rho \sin(\theta)} - \psi(H_\varphi)$
7	$\text{rot}_\varphi H$	$\frac{H_\theta}{\rho} + \frac{\partial H_\theta}{\partial \rho} - \frac{\partial H_\rho}{\rho \partial \varphi}$	$\psi(H_\theta) - \frac{i\alpha H_\rho}{\rho}$
4	$\text{div}(E)$	$\frac{E_\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial E_\rho}{\partial \rho} + \frac{E_\theta}{\rho g(\theta)} + \frac{\partial E_\theta}{\rho \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi}$	$\psi(E_\rho) + \frac{T(E_\theta)}{\rho} + \frac{i\alpha E_\varphi}{\rho \sin(\theta)}$
8	$\text{div}(H)$	$\frac{H_\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial H_\rho}{\partial \rho} + \frac{H_\theta}{\rho g(\theta)} + \frac{\partial H_\theta}{\rho \partial \theta} + \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\rho \sin(\theta) \partial \varphi}$	$\psi(H_\rho) + \frac{T(H_\theta)}{\rho} + \frac{i\alpha H_\varphi}{\rho \sin(\theta)}$

Table 1A.

1	2	3
1.	$\text{rot}_\rho E + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H_\rho}{\partial t} = 0$	$\frac{T(E_\varphi)}{\rho} + \frac{i\omega\mu H_\rho}{c} = 0$
5.	$\text{rot}_\rho H - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E_\rho}{\partial t} = 0$	$\frac{T(H_\varphi)}{\rho} - \frac{i\omega\varepsilon E_\rho}{c}$
2.	$\text{rot}_\theta E + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H_\theta}{\partial t} = 0$	$-\Psi(E_\varphi) + \frac{i\omega\mu H_\theta}{c} = 0$
3.	$\text{rot}_\varphi E + \frac{\mu}{c} \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\partial t} = 0$	$\Psi(E_\theta) + \frac{i\omega\mu H_\varphi}{c} = 0$
6.	$\text{rot}_\theta H - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E_\theta}{\partial t} = 0$	$-\Psi(H_\varphi) - \frac{i\omega\varepsilon E_\theta}{c} = 0$
7.	$\text{rot}_\varphi H - \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\partial t} = 0$	$\Psi(H_\theta) - \frac{i\omega\varepsilon E_\varphi}{c} = 0$
4.	$\text{div}(E) = 0$	$\Psi(E_\rho) + \frac{T(E_\theta)}{\rho} = 0$
8.	$\text{div}(H) = 0$	$\Psi(H_\rho) + \frac{T(H_\theta)}{\rho} = 0$

Table 2.

1	2
	$E_\theta = e_\theta \sin(\theta) \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t)$
	$E_\varphi = e_\varphi \sin(\theta) \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t)$
	$E_\rho = \cos(\theta) \left(e_\rho \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t) + \bar{e}_\rho \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t) \right)$
	$J_\rho = \cos(\theta) \left(j_\rho \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t) + \bar{j}_\rho \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t) \right)$
	$H_\theta = h_\theta \sin(\theta) \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t)$
	$H_\varphi = h_\varphi \sin(\theta) \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t)$
	$H_\rho = \cos(\theta) \left(h_\rho \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t) + \bar{h}_\rho \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t) \right)$
	$M_\rho = \cos(\theta) \left(m_\rho \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t) + \bar{m}_\rho \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t) \right)$

Table 2i.

1	2
	$i\omega E_\theta = \omega \sin(\theta) (-e_\theta \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$i\omega E_\varphi = \omega \sin(\theta) (e_\varphi \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$i\omega E_\rho = \omega \cos(\theta) (-e_\rho \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t) + \bar{e}_\rho \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$i\omega H_\theta = \omega \sin(\theta) (h_\theta \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$i\omega H_\varphi = \omega \sin(\theta) (-h_\varphi \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$i\omega H_\rho = \omega \cos(\theta) (h_\rho \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t) - \bar{h}_\rho \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t))$

Table 2ρ.

1	2
	$\frac{\partial E_\theta}{\partial \rho} = \chi \sin(\theta) (-e_\theta \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$\frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\partial \rho} = \chi \sin(\theta) (e_\varphi \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$\frac{\partial E_\rho}{\partial \rho} = \chi \cos(\theta) (-e_\rho \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t) + \bar{e}_\rho \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$\frac{\partial H_\theta}{\partial \rho} = \chi \sin(\theta) (-h_\varphi \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$\frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\partial \rho} = \chi \sin(\theta) (-h_\varphi \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t))$
	$\frac{\partial H_\rho}{\partial \rho} = \chi \cos(\theta) (h_\rho \cos(\chi\rho + \omega t) - \bar{h}_\rho \sin(\chi\rho + \omega t))$

Table 2Ψ.

2
$\Psi(E_\theta) = \frac{E_\theta}{\rho} + \frac{\partial E_\theta}{\partial \rho} = \sin(\theta) \left(\frac{1}{\rho} (e_\theta \text{co}) + \chi(-e_\theta \text{si}) + (\overline{[e_\theta] \text{co}}) \right)$
$\Psi(E_\varphi) = \frac{E_\varphi}{\rho} + \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\partial \rho} = \sin(\theta) \left(\frac{1}{\rho} (e_\varphi \text{si}) + \chi(e_\varphi \text{co}) + (\overline{[e_\varphi] \text{si}}) \right)$
$\begin{aligned} \Psi(E_\rho) &= \frac{E_\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial E_\rho}{\partial \rho} \\ &= \cos(\theta) \left(\frac{1}{\rho} (e_\rho \text{co}) + \frac{1}{\rho} (\overline{e}_\rho \text{si}) + \chi(\overline{e}_\rho \text{co}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \chi(e_\rho \text{si}) + (\overline{[e_\rho] \text{co}}) + (\overline{[\overline{e}_\rho] \text{si}}) \right) \end{aligned}$
$\Psi(H_\theta) = \frac{H_\theta}{\rho} + \frac{\partial H_\theta}{\partial \rho} = \sin(\theta) \left(\frac{1}{\rho} (h_\theta \text{si}) + \chi(h_\theta \text{co}) + (\overline{[h_\theta] \text{si}}) \right)$
$\Psi(H_\varphi) = \frac{H_\varphi}{\rho} + \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\partial \rho} = \sin(\theta) \left(\frac{1}{\rho} (h_\varphi \text{co}) + \chi(-h_\varphi \text{si}) + (\overline{[h_\varphi] \text{co}}) \right)$
$\begin{aligned} \Psi(H_\rho) &= \frac{H_\rho}{\rho} + \frac{\partial H_\rho}{\partial \rho} \\ &= \cos(\theta) \left(\frac{1}{\rho} (h_\rho \text{si}) + \frac{1}{\rho} (\overline{h}_\rho \text{co}) - \chi(\overline{h}_\rho \text{si}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \chi(h_\rho \text{co}) + (\overline{[h_\rho] \text{si}}) + (\overline{[\overline{h}_\rho] \text{co}}) \right) \end{aligned}$

Table 4.

1	2
1.	$\frac{2}{\rho}(e_{\varphi} \text{si}) - \frac{\mu}{c}\omega(\bar{h}_{\rho} \text{si}) = j_{\rho} \text{si}$ $\frac{\mu}{c}\omega(h_{\rho} \text{co}) = \bar{j}_{\rho} \text{co}$
5.	$\frac{2}{\rho}(h_{\varphi} \text{co}) + \frac{\varepsilon}{c}\omega(\bar{e}_{\rho} \text{co}) = m_{\rho} \text{co}$ $\frac{\varepsilon}{c}\omega(e_{\rho} \text{si}) = \bar{m}_{\rho} \text{si}$
2.	$-\left(\frac{1}{\rho}(e_{\varphi} \text{si}) + \chi(e_{\varphi} \text{co}) + (\boxed{e_{\varphi}} \text{si})\right) + \frac{\mu}{c}\omega(h_{\theta} \text{co}) = 0$
3.	$\left(\frac{1}{\rho}(e_{\theta} \text{co}) + \chi(-e_{\theta} \text{si}) + (\boxed{e_{\theta}} \text{co})\right) + \frac{\mu}{c}\omega(-h_{\varphi} \text{si}) = 0$
6.	$-\left(\frac{1}{\rho}(h_{\varphi} \text{co}) + \chi(-h_{\varphi} \text{si}) + (\boxed{h_{\varphi}} \text{co})\right) - \frac{\varepsilon}{c}\omega(-e_{\theta} \text{si}) = 0$
7.	$\left(\frac{1}{\rho}(h_{\theta} \text{si}) + \chi(h_{\theta} \text{co}) + (\boxed{h_{\theta}} \text{si})\right) - \frac{\varepsilon}{c}\omega(e_{\varphi} \text{co}) = 0$
4.	$\left(\frac{1}{\rho}(e_{\rho} \text{co}) + \chi(\bar{e}_{\rho} \text{co}) + (\boxed{e_{\rho}} \text{co})\right) + \frac{2}{\rho}(e_{\theta} \text{co}) = 0$ $\left(\frac{1}{\rho}(\bar{e}_{\rho} \text{si}) - \chi(e_{\rho} \text{si}) + (\boxed{\bar{e}_{\rho}} \text{si})\right) = 0$
8.	$\left(\frac{1}{\rho}(h_{\rho} \text{si}) - \chi(\bar{h}_{\rho} \text{si}) + (\boxed{h_{\rho}} \text{si})\right) + \frac{2}{\rho}(h_{\theta} \text{si}) = 0$ $\left(\frac{1}{\rho}(\bar{h}_{\rho} \text{co}) + \chi(h_{\rho} \text{co}) + (\boxed{\bar{h}_{\rho}} \text{co})\right) = 0$

Table 5

1	2
1.	$\frac{2}{\rho} e_\varphi - \frac{\mu}{c} \omega \bar{h}_\rho = j_\rho; \frac{\mu}{c} \omega h_\rho = \bar{j}_\rho$
5.	$\frac{2}{\rho} h_\varphi + \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \omega \bar{e}_\rho = m_\rho; \frac{\varepsilon}{c} \omega e_\rho = \bar{m}_\rho$
2.	$\boxed{e_\varphi} = -\chi e_\varphi - \frac{1}{\rho} e_\varphi + \frac{\mu\omega}{c} h_\varphi$
6.	$\boxed{h_\varphi} = \chi h_\varphi - \frac{1}{\rho} h_\varphi - \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_\theta$
3.	$\boxed{e_\theta} = \chi e_\theta - \frac{1}{\rho} e_\theta - \frac{\mu\omega}{c} h_\varphi$
7.	$\boxed{h_\theta} = -\chi h_\theta - \frac{1}{\rho} h_\theta + \frac{\varepsilon\omega}{c} e_\varphi$
4.	1 $\left(\frac{1}{\rho} e_\rho + \chi \bar{e}_\rho + \boxed{e_\rho}\right) + \frac{2}{\rho} e_\theta = 0$
	2 $\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \bar{e}_\rho - \chi e_\rho + \boxed{\bar{e}_\rho}\right) = 0$
8.	1 $\left(\frac{1}{\rho} h_\rho - \chi \bar{h}_\rho + \boxed{h_\rho}\right) + \frac{2}{\rho} h_\theta = 0$
	2 $\left(\frac{1}{\rho} \bar{h}_\rho + \chi h_\rho + \boxed{\bar{h}_\rho}\right) = 0$